

Impact of initial chloride contaminations on the corrosion rate evolution of reinforced Belite-Ye'elinite-Ferrite (BYF) cement mortars

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Abstract

Portland cement has become an essential building material in the last century. Its production unfortunately leads to noticeable CO₂-emissions. The development of Belite-Yeelinite-Ferrite (BYF) cement as alternative binder is a promising solution with a decrease of 20-30% in CO₂ emissions. One important issue for this new cement is its ability to passivate mild steel. Only few results about it are currently available due to the relatively new nature of the technology. This paper discusses the electrochemical behavior of steel in a BYF matrix. The impact of chloride (present in raw materials as permissible impurities) was considered too. An ordinary Portland cement was used as reference. Mortar specimens with embedded steel rebar were cast with varying chloride contents (0.0, 0.2, 0.4 and 1.0% of chloride by mass of cement). Electrochemical techniques such as half-cell readings, linear polarization resistance (LPR) and large potentiodynamic polarizations were carried out. Specimens contaminated by chloride up to 0.4% showed low corrosion rate (< 1 μm/year) during the first year of measurements. High corrosion activity (>5 μm/year) was yet observed with a chloride content of 1.0% by mass of cement. Therefore steel embedded in BYF mortar passivates and a chloride content up to 0.4% by mass of cement can be tolerated. The contamination by 1% of chloride by mass of cement (not allowed for reinforced concrete made with Portland cement according to the European standard EN 206) leads to active corrosion.

Keywords: Corrosion, Chloride, Cement, Yeelinite, Innovative binder.

1. Introduction

The production of cement is responsible of about 5% of the global anthropogenic CO₂ emissions [1]. The cement industry is aware of this issue and different measures have been implemented as the use of alternative fuels or raw materials for the manufacture of Portland-based cements and the extent of the use of low-carbon supplementary cementitious materials (SCM) in blended Portland cement. Long-term actions are under study as the capture and sequestration of the CO₂ emissions, or the development of alternative binders not based on Portland [2]. As part of this initiative, a new type of clinker, called Belite-Yeelimate-Ferrite (BYF), is under study. In comparison to Portland clinker, fabrication of BYF clinker requires less calcium carbonate in the raw mix, and the clinkering temperature is lower (usually 1250°C instead of 1450°C). When mixed to calcium sulfate and SCM eventually, we obtain new binders with reduced CO₂-emissions in comparison to the existing Portland cements.

The behaviour of black steel embedded in BYF-based concrete is an item to investigate for a wide use of BYF cements. Indeed these new binders represent a real alternative if the related cements can be used to make reinforced concrete. Concrete having a relatively low tensile strength is usually reinforced with black steel rebar embedded before concrete sets. There is no need to use special reinforcement like stainless steel or galvanized steel. Black steel has a very low corrosion rate when embedded in concrete made with ordinary Portland cement. A protective layer of oxide/hydroxide of iron forms thanks to the high alkalinity of concrete due to hydration of Portland cement.

It has been shown that comparable passivation of black steel can be obtained with particular BYF cement [3]. This paper discusses if steel passivation would be hindered by the presence of chloride initially in the concrete mix.

Chloride ions are everywhere at once. They can be present in varying amounts in the raw materials of concrete, such as sea dredged aggregates which are unwashed or inadequately washed, brackish mixing water, contaminated supplementary cementitious materials, admixtures [4,5]. The total chloride content of a concrete mix-design, meaning the sum of the amounts of chloride of the raw materials, is limited by standards. The common European framework for concrete standard EN 206 defines several classes of chloride content. The maximum permissible chloride content is 0.4% of chloride by mass of cement for concrete containing steel reinforcement, and 0.2% for concrete containing prestressing steel reinforcement. A chloride content below these limiting values is deemed to allow steel passivation for a given service life. In presence of chloride in higher quantity, the passivating layer cannot form on steel surface, pitting corrosion being predominant.

The study consisted in electrochemical measurements on steel reinforced mortar samples made with a BYF cement. The goal was to examine the effect of chloride when present at 0.2 or 0.4% by mass of BYF cement. Half-cell measurements, linear polarization resistance technique, and electrochemical impedance spectroscopy were performed to assess the corrosion behavior of rebars embedded in mortars over time. Some experiments were carried out with 1% of chloride by mass of cement to evaluate the discriminating side of the experimental procedure. An ordinary Portland cement (CEM I 52.5 N) was included in the study as reference. The layer formed of iron oxides/hydroxides would be considered as protective enough if the corrosion rate is low enough, meaning below < 1 µm/year [6].

2. Experimental

2.1 Materials

The experiments have been performed with black steel ribbed rebars ($\text{\O}14$ mm, 130 mm length). The chemical composition of the steel in this study is provided in table 1.

Table 1 Steel elemental composition (mean values of four analyses, three at the edge and one at the center of cross section samples, which gave exactly the same chemical composition.)

Chemical composition (wt.%)									
C ^a	S ^a	Cu	Ni	Si	Cr	Mo	Mn	P	Fe
0.21	0.03	0.430	0.210	0.200	0.068	0.041	0.720	0.011	bal.

^a Chemical determination by high frequency furnace and infrared detection. The others elements were determined by spark optical emission spectrometry

As Figure 1a and b show, the microstructure of the reinforcement used in the present study is composed by a core of α -Fe matrix with perlite islands and the edge of martensite from quenching. Note the presence of superficial ferrous oxide, also known as mill scale, in Figure 1b.

Figure 1 Cross section optical micrographs 500X after Nital 2% etching from a) the core of the sample and b) the edge where is possible to see the presence of a thin non-adherent and heterogeneous mill scale.

Two cements were considered for the study: a prototype of BYF cement and a commercial Portland cement (CEM I 52.5 N from the Lafarge cement plant at St Pierre La Cour in France). The main characteristics of the cement are given the table 2.

Table 2 Composition of OPC and BYF cements used in the present study.

CEM I 52.5 N CE				BYF cement (prototype)			
Chemical analysis ^a		Phase composition ^b		Chemical analysis ^a		Phase composition ^b	
g/100g		g/100g		g/100g		g/100g	
SiO ₂	20.29	Alite	60.2	SiO ₂	13.03	Ye'elimite	31.1
Al ₂ O ₃	4.87	β-C ₂ S	17.9	Al ₂ O ₃	17.48	α'-C ₂ S	29
Fe ₂ O ₃	3.11	C ₃ A	5.1	Fe ₂ O ₃	6.38	β-C ₂ S	8
CaO	63.79	Ferrite	10.5	CaO	47.82	Ferrite	20.9
MgO	1.08	Gypsum	1.8	MgO	1.51	Anhydrite	6.5
K ₂ O	0.91	Hemihydrate	1.8	K ₂ O	0.68	Gypsum	1.5
Na ₂ O	0.16	Calcite	1.5	Na ₂ O	0.07	Periclase	0.9
SO ₃	3.2	Periclase	0.1	SO ₃	8.78	Other phases	2.7
TiO ₂	0.24	CaO	1.1	TiO ₂	0.9	Readily soluble alkalis ^c	
Mn ₂ O ₃	0.11	Readily soluble alkalis ^c		Mn ₂ O ₃	0.07	K ₂ O	0.36
P ₂ O ₅	0.26	K ₂ O	0.77	P ₂ O ₅	0.06	Na ₂ O	0.02
L.O.I.	1.57	Na ₂ O	0.07	L.O.I.	2.4		

a) X-ray Fluorescence analysis.

b) Rietveld analysis

c) ICP-AES.

2.2 Electrochemical measurements

2.2.1 Sample preparation

The samples were cylinders of mortar with steel rebar embedded in the center (lollipops). The steps to get a lollipop are depicted in the figure below.

Before casting, the steel rebars were first cleaned with ethyl alcohol to remove grease. The superficial rust was removed but not the mill scale. The top and bottom ends of the steel rebars were insulated with epoxy resin first and then a layer of heat-shrink tube over it. Thus, the exposed surface of the steel was approximately 31 cm². The rebars were then placed in the center in a hollow cylinder, and embedded with fresh mortar made according to the standard NF EN 196-1.

Figure 2 a) Description of the lollipops of the study b) Steps of preparation

Three mix-designs of mortar were considered, one made the OPC of reference and two made with the BYF cement and two values of water to cement ratio (see table 3). Different amounts of high purity (> 99.5%) sodium chloride were dissolved in the mixing water. The amounts correspond to 0, 0.2, 0.4 and 1 % of the mass of the cement. The molds were hermetically sealed and kept for 24 h at 20 ± 1 °C before demolding. The obtained samples, called “lollipops” were stored in a humid chamber regulated at 20 ± 1 °C and 90-95% of relative humidity. Under these conditions of humidity, the cements can hydrate and gaseous dioxygen can migrate until the steel rebars as the samples are not fully saturated of water. Under these conditions, all the conditions are reunified to promote any eventual steel of corrosion: steel, humidity, gaseous dioxygen.

Table 3 Mortar mixtures used in the production of different reinforced mortars.

	Mix label		
	OPC (0.50)	BYF (0.50)	BYF (0.67)
Cement type	OPC	BYF	BYF
Water to cement ratio (W/C)	0.50	0.50	0.67
Aggregate / Cement weight ratio	3	3	3
Superplasticizer (% by cement weight)	0	0.1	0
Initial chloride content (wt.% cement)	0; 0.2; 0.4; 1.0	0; 0.2; 0.4; 1.0	0; 0.2; 0.4; 1.0

Figure 3 Schematic illustration of the protocol to produce cylindrical reinforced mortar specimens (called lollipop) for electrochemical tests. High purity NaCl was dissolved in the mixing water in order to introduce the targeted Cl⁻ content (0, 0.2, 0.4, 1 wt.% of Cl⁻ by cement weight).

2.2.2 Electrochemical techniques

Figure 4 shows the corrosion cell used to carry out DC and AC measurements. The working electrode was the embedded steel rebar and the electrolyte the interstitial pore solution of mortar. The counter electrode was placed on the external surface of the mortar which was surrounded by a moist sponge band to ensure proper electrical connection. The counter electrode was a co-axial carbon sheet, which provided uniformly distributed electric field; hence a reasonably large surface was analyzed (31 cm²). The electrode of reference (RE) was a saturated calomel electrode (SCE) one, placed perpendicularly to the axis of the rebar axis, in contact with the sponge in a hole of 15 mm diameter of the CE. The tip of the SCE reference electrode was therefore in contact with the same pre-wetted sponge that assured electrical connection with the counter-electrode.

Figure 4 Schematic of the test set-up used to perform electrochemical measurements on lollipop samples.

The electrochemical measurements were performed at several times for one year. The specimens used in destructive electrochemical methods were discarded after each test. A BioLogic potentiostat SP-300 with impedance channels was used in the present work.

Half-cell readings were recorded versus time at room temperature (20 ± 2 °C). The data acquisition and interpretation were based on the ASTM C876-09 [7] and RILEM TC 154-EMC [8]. Four different samples were monitored for repeatability.

LPR measurements were carried out on the same samples by using scan rate of 0.167 mV/s and potential amplitude of 20 mV, starting at 10 mV in negative direction with respect to the open circuit potential. The apparent polarization resistance, $R_{p(\text{app})}$, was obtained by means of the $\Delta E/\Delta j$ ratio determination in the linear region of anodic domain. The real polarization resistance, $R_{p(\text{real})}$, was estimated after compensation of the ohmic drop (IR) due to the electrolyte resistance, R_e . In this case, the diameter of first semi-circle of the Nyquist electrochemical impedance diagram was taken as R_e . The electrolyte resistance was then discounted from $R_{p(\text{app})}$ manually after LPR measurements. The corrosion current density, j_{corr} , was calculated through the Stern-Geary expression ($j_{\text{corr}} = B/R_{p(\text{real})}$), where a value of 26 mV was given to the coefficient B which is recommended for on-site measurements.

Pitting or localized corrosion are potential factors that may bias the corrosion measurements through LPR technique [9]. However, some recommendations and methodologies to improve the reliability on the corrosion rates assessment of non-uniform corrosion of reinforced concretes by LRP techniques do exist (e.g. Andrade et al. [6], and references therein). Even so, additional measurements should be conducted in order to minimise incorrect interpretations. That is why large potentiodynamic polarization was carried out after one year. Anodic and cathodic curves were obtained separately. The polarization of each anodic or cathodic branch started with a little polarization ($|\pi| = 30$ mV) in opposite direction and then a polarization ($|\pi| = 1000$ mV) in desired direction, both with respect to the open circuit potential, E_{oc} . The scan rate used was 0.167 mV/s.

2.2.3 Criteria for steel passivation

The state of corrosion of steel embedded in BYF- or OPC-based mortars will be evaluated according to the Tafel and LPR measurements. Immediately after the fabrication of the samples, in the absence of any passivating layer, the current density is expected to be high. The formation of an oxy/hydroxide layer should then induce a decrease of the current density and an increase of the half-cell potential. The level of protection can be evaluated according to the value of the current density. If the current density (j_{corr}) is below $0.1 \mu\text{A}/\text{cm}^2$ [6], the corrosion rate will be considered as very low. The protection is considered as not satisfying enough above $0.2 \mu\text{A}/\text{cm}^2$.

The open circuit potential (E_{corr}) is also helpful to qualify the state of the embedded steel. The criteria considered are those mentioned in [7], adapted for our reference electrode: a low-corrosion risk correspond to potential values above -126 mV/SCE and a high risk of corrosion to values below -276 mV/SCE. The criteria based on potential is not as an absolute one as can be the current density.

In addition, the specimens were split along the embedded rebar to observe particularly the steel/concrete interface after one year of conservation. The visual inspection is useful to confirm the electrochemical indications.

3. Results

3.1 Reinforced OPC mortar (w/c = 0.50)

Figure 5 a) and b) depict respectively the evolution of $E_{\text{half-cell}}$ and j_{corr} values over one year for reinforced OPC mortars with varying chloride contents.

With 0.2 and 0.4% of Cl, the potential readings of specimens were first slightly lower values. This slight difference disappeared after 210 days. The potential values were above the limit -126 mV/SCE after 150 days, which should correspond to a low-corrosion risk. The measured current densities values, Fig. 5b, corroborate this trend: the values of current density decreased from $0.4/0.5 \mu\text{A/cm}^2$ to values below $0.1 \mu\text{A/cm}^2$ after 28 days of conservation.

A different evolution has been observed for the samples made with 1% Cl. The values of $E_{\text{half-cell}}$ were considerably lower: the values were inferior to -276 mV/SCE for 210 days, and then below -126 mV/SCE . The current density decreased from $1.8 \mu\text{A/cm}^2$ to values around $0.5 \mu\text{A/cm}^2$ ($> 0.2 \mu\text{A/cm}^2$).

Figure 5a) Half-cell potential readings over time of reinforced OPC mortar with different Cl contents; **b)** Corrosion current density, j_{corr} , calculated from LPR measurements through Stern-Geary relationship using $B = 26 \text{ mV}$. Lines intended as eye guide following the empirical criteria for probability of corrosion suggested by ASTM C876 [7] and by RILEM recommendations [6] were included.

Figure 6 shows the anodic polarization curves. There is a slight difference between the anodic polarization curves up to 0.4% of chloride. The corresponding E_{corr} and j_{corr} show a satisfying level of protection due to steel passivation up to 0.4% of chloride by mass of cement. On the contrary, reinforced OPC mortar with 1% Cl clearly presents higher j_{corr} compared to the other samples as consequence of the poor protecting layer over the steel surface, if any. The results obtained with the anodic polarization curves are in agreement with the LPR measurements.

Figure 6 Anodic polarization curves, after 365 days, for reinforced OPC mortars with different Cl contents.

A lollipop of each series was splitted after one year of conservation at 20°C and 90-95%RH (Figure 7). There was no corrosion sign for the specimens up to 0.4% Cl. On the contrary, we can observe some spots of corrosion product (brown rust) for the specimens with 1% Cl. These spots formed on the ribs of the reinforcement, these regions being more prone to present higher densities of metallurgical defects and residual stress.

Figure 7 Visual inspection, after 1 year, of steel reinforcements embedded in OPC mortars with different Cl content: 0.0%, 0.2%, 0.4%, and 1.0% by cement mass.

To conclude, the different types of measurement performed (Half-cell potential, LPR and anodic polarization) are in good agreement. The addition up to 0.4% Cl by mass of OPC

in the initial mix did not avoid the formation of a high protecting layer. In presence of 1% of chloride, the measurements show the formation of a layer that induced a diminution of the current density. But this layer did not provide an adequate level of protection.

3.2 Reinforced BYF mortar (w/c = 0.50)

The evolution of $E_{\text{half-cell}}$ and j_{corr} over time for reinforced BYF mortars with w/c = 0.50 are given in *Figure 8a)* and *b)* respectively.

The potential was lower in presence of chloride than without chloride. For the series with 0.2 and 0.4% of chloride, the potential increased with time but there is a permanent shift of -100 to -150 mV with the curve of reference without chloride. The potential reached the limit of -276 mV/SCE after 90 days and -126 mV/SCE after one year. The situation is different for the series with 1% Cl: the potential remains around -500 mV/SCE.

As can be seen in the figure 8 b), the current density was higher than $0.2 \mu\text{A}/\text{cm}^2$ within the first days after steel embedding. The initial values vary in function of the chloride content. Then the current density decreased during the first month. For the reference without chloride, the current density was below the limit of $0.1 \mu\text{A}/\text{cm}^2$ after two weeks while the samples with chloride remain above $0.2 \mu\text{A}/\text{cm}^2$ for 60 days. The current density of the samples made with 0.2 and 0.4% of chloride by mass of cement continued to decrease with time, until $0.1 \mu\text{A}/\text{cm}^2$ after 210 days. On the contrary, the values of current density for samples with 1% of chloride remain relatively high with strong differences between the samples (large standard deviation).

Figure 8 Electrochemical measurements over time for reinforced BYF (w/c = 0.50) with different Cl contents **a)** half-cell potential readings; **b)** corrosion current density, j_{corr} calculated from LPR measurements through Stern-Geary relationship using $B = 26 \text{ mV}$. Lines intended as eye guide as for Figure 5.

Figure 9 depicts the anodic polarization curves of reinforced BYF mortars (w/c = 0.50) after 1 year of curing. In comparison to the curve of reference without chloride, the curves corresponding to the samples with 0.2 and 0.4% of chloride by mass of BYF cement were shifted to slightly lower values of potential and higher values of current density. The current density deduced of the curve was nevertheless lower than $0.1 \mu\text{A}/\text{cm}$, corresponding to a

satisfying level of protection with the passivating layer formed. The anodic curve corresponding to samples with 1% Cl was shifted to strongly lower values of potential and higher values of current density (one order of magnitude when compared to reinforced samples without chloride).

Figure 9 Anodic potentiodynamic curves, after 365 days, of reinforced BYF mortars ($w/c = 0.50$) contaminated with 0.0, 0.2, 0.4, and 1.0% Cl by cement weight.

The visual examination after one year is in agreement with the electrochemical results (Figure 10). No corrosion products were observed for specimen without Cl. With 0.2 and 0.4% of chloride, we can observe some small spots of brown rust certainly formed at early-age when the current density was higher than $0.2 \mu\text{A}/\text{cm}^2$. Large areas of corrosion products were observed for the sample containing 1% of equivalent chloride, as a consequence of the high corrosion rates during one year of testing. The spots are mainly localized at the ribs, as observed for the OPC specimens, Figure 7.

Figure 10 Visual inspection, after 1 year, of steel reinforcements embedded in BYF mortars ($w/c = 0.5$) with different Cl content: 0.0%, 0.2%, 0.4%, and 1.0% by mass of cement.

To summarize, the presence of chloride induced higher values of current density and lower potential values within the first days after the fabrication of samples with the tested BYF cement. When chloride was limited to 0.2 and 0.4% by mass of BYF cement, the potential evolved to higher values and the current density to lower ones, corresponding to the formation of a passivating layer. The steel protection level can be considered as strong enough after 210 days. On the contrary, the addition of 1% Cl avoided the passivation of the steel reinforcement for one year and the steel is considered in active state.

3.3 Reinforced BYF mortar ($w/c = 0.67$)

Similar measurements were carried out in the same conditions with samples made the same BYF cement and a higher water to cement ratio (0.67 instead of 0.50). The goal was evaluate the robustness of the effect of chloride with a higher water to cement ratio.

The evolution of the potential and the current density for samples with 0 and 0.2% Cl are similar than for the BYF samples with a water to cement ratio of 0.5. In presence of 0.4% of chloride, the evolution is less favourable. Despite a noticeable decrease of the values, the current density was around 0.3-0.4 $\mu\text{A}/\text{cm}^2$ even after one year.

For samples cast with 1% of chloride, the potential remain low and the current density very high (around 2 $\mu\text{A}/\text{cm}^2$). The high corrosion rates caused premature cracking of reinforced BYF specimens with $w/c = 0.67$ only after 210 days of survey.

Figure 11 Electrochemical measurements over time for reinforced BYF ($w/c = 0.67$) with different Cl contents a) half-cell potential readings; b) corrosion current density, j_{corr} , calculated from LPR measurements through Stern-Geary relationship using $B = 26 \text{ mV}$. Lines intended as eye guide as for Figure 5.

Figure 12 shows the anodic polarization curves conducted after 365 days of curing. It can be seen that the j_{corr} of reinforced BYF ($w/c=0.67$) samples with 0.2% Cl is negligible ($j_{\text{corr}} < 0.1 \mu\text{m}/\text{cm}^2$). However, 0.4% Cl impaired the passivation of the reinforcement in such that the resulting j_{corr} is too high. In addition of the impediment of the passivation, the addition of 1.0% Cl has induced high corrosion, Figure 11 and Figure 12.

Figure 12 Anodic potentiodynamic curves, after 365 days, of reinforced BYF mortars ($w/c = 0.50$) contaminated with 0, 0.2, 0.4, and 1% Cl by cement weight.

After one year, one sample of each series was split and visually examined after one year (Figure 13). It is interesting to note that even the Cl-free samples presented little corrosion spots, probably due to the presence of water pockets around the ribs after casting (bleeding). The Cl addition induced a more pronounced corrosion of 1% of chloride. Considering that the j_{corr} for samples contaminated with 0.2% Cl drops to negligible levels after 60 days, the corrosion products observed can be ascribed mostly to this period.

Figure 13 Visual inspections, after 1 year, of steel reinforcements embedded in BYF mortars ($w/c = 50$) with different Cl content: 0.0%, 0.2%, 0.4%, and 1.0%.

To summarize, a concentration of chloride corresponding to 0.2% by mass of BYF cement allows the formation of a passivating film with a satisfying level of protection for BYF samples made with a water to cement ratio of 0.67. A concentration of 0.4% allows the formation of layer but with an inadequate protection level for steel. With a concentration of 1%, the corrosion rate was so high that some samples cracked before the end of the one year period of the survey.

4 Discussion

After one year, the corrosion rate of black steel rebar embedded in OPC- or BYF-based mortar is finally the same with chloride up to 0.4% by mass of cement, when the water to cement ratio is limited to 0.5. A passivating layer seems to form with a similar protection level whatever the cement type. The main difference is that the initial current density is more sensitive to the presence of chloride with the BYF cement than with OPC. This can be explained by the pH of pore solution within the first hour of hydration: around 13.5 with OPC and 10.5 with the tested BYF. In this latter case, the pH is regulated by the hydration process of Yeelimité in presence of calcium sulphate as it is for hydration of calcium sulfoaluminate cement [10,11]. The pH of the pore solution then increased with the hydration of belite and ferrite [10]. When present at 0.2 or 0.4% by mass of cement, chloride ions seem to be more

active in the range of lower pH, but without hindering the formation of passivating layer when the hydration go further.

The water to cement ratio has an effect on porosity of the cement paste which, in turn, impact the availability of moisture, oxygen content, and defects at the steel/mortar interface [18]. As a result, the risk of pitting corrosion increase with decreasing w/b ratio [19]. This can explain why the series of samples BYF (w/c=0.67) are more sensitive to chloride induced corrosion.

The presence of 1% of chloride by mass of cement hindered the formation of protective layer whatever the cement type and the water to cement ratio tested. The pitting corrosion was predominant and the corrosion rate remained high for one year. This shows that the experimental procedure carried out is discriminating enough and justify why this chloride content in not allowed by the standards.

A calculation was carried out to evaluate the impact of the initial corrosion on one year. The penetration attack function, $P(t)$, represents the loss of rebar diameter at time t. Thus, the penetration damage attack until passivation can be estimated by:

$$P(t) = \int_{t_i}^{t_p} V_{corr}(t) dt \quad (\text{Eq.1})$$

where $V_{corr}(t)$ is the corrosion rate at instant t, and t_p is the time to passivation. Several studies correlate the penetration attack that generates enough expansive oxide growth to cause cracking [12–15]. Most of the research work is limited to accelerated corrosion testing of reinforced concrete. Additionally, the results are influenced by the testing method including the level of impressed current, cover depth, reinforcing bar diameter, concrete properties, rust products, etc [16]. Despite these specificities, the reported corrosion penetration that would generate expansion to cause cracking is ranging from 6 to 160 μm . Both the corrosion penetration attack induced before passivation of reinforced BYF mortar with 0.2% Cl (0.85 μm) and with 0.4% Cl (0.87 μm) are low in comparison with the penetration attack range which has been reported to induce cracking of the cementitious cover layer. As a result, the admissible chloride content in reinforced BYF mortars with w/c = 0.50 is 0.4% Cl by mass of cement which is in agreement upper limit proposed for reinforced OPC concretes [17].

A mean value, j_{mean} , was obtained by integrating the j_{corr} -time curves (from 1 to 365 days) and dividing it by the number of days as in [20,21]. Figure 14 shows the j_{mean} values for reinforced BYF and OPC specimens. These values take into account the active and passive periods over 365 days. Cl free samples presented low j_{mean} ($< 0.2 \mu\text{A}/\text{cm}^2$) regardless the cement type or the w/c ratio. On the other hand, samples contaminated with 1.0% Cl showed high j_{mean} in all cases. With respect to the 0.4% Cl, the OPC samples showed negligible j_{mean} as well as the BYF (w/c=0.50). However, 0.4% Cl is not tolerated to BYF (w/c=0.67) since the calculated j_{mean} is superior to $0.2 \mu\text{A}/\text{cm}^2$.

Figure 14 j_{mean} (from 1 to 365 days) for different Cl contents and different reinforced samples.

Conclusion:

- Steel rebar passivate in Cl free samples regardless the cement type (BYF or OPC) or the water to cement ratio (0.50, 0.67).
- Initial Cl contents up to 0.4% by mass of cement are permissible, regarding corrosion, to both reinforced BYF and OPC cement mortar with water to cement ratio equals to 0.50.
- Higher values of water to cement ratio decrease the acceptable Cl content from 0.4% Cl by mass of BYF cement (w/c=0.50) to 0.2% (w/c=0.67).

References

- [1] I.E. Agency, Cement roadmap, (2016). https://www.iea.org/publications/freepublications/publication/Cement_Roadmap_Fold_out_WEB.pdf (accessed February 4, 2016).
- [2] E. Gartner, H. Hiraio, A review of alternative approaches to the reduction of CO2 emissions associated with the manufacture of the binder phase in concrete, *Cem. Concr. Res.* 78 (2015) 126–142. doi:10.1016/j.cemconres.2015.04.012.
- [3] G.Y. Koga, R.P. Nogueira, B. Albert, B. Huet, V. Morin, Corrosion behavior of black steel embedded in BYF cement mortars, in: *Proc. 35th Cem. Concr. Sci. Conf.*, Aberdeen, 2015.
- [4] L. Bertolini, B. Elsener, P. Pedferri, R.P. Polder, *Corrosion of steel in concrete: Prevention, Diagnosis, Repair*, WILEY-VCH Verlag GmbH & Co. KGaA, Weinheim, 2004.
- [5] J.P. Broomfield, *Causes and mechanisms of corrosion and corrosion damage in*

- concrete, in: *Corros. Steel Concr. Understanding, Investig. Repair*, E & FN SPON, London and New York, 2003: p. 239.
- [6] C. Andrade, C. Alonso, R. Polder, R. Cigna, O. Vennesland, M. Salta, et al., Test methods for on-site corrosion rate measurement of steel reinforcement in concrete by means of the polarization resistance method, *Mater. Struct.* 37 (2004) 623–643.
- [7] ASTM C876-09. Standard Test Method for Half-Cell Potentials of Uncoated Reinforcing Steel in Concrete, ASTM International, West Conshohocken, 2009. doi:10.1520/C0876-09.2.
- [8] B. Elsener, C. Andrade, J. Gulikers, R. Polder, M. Raupach, Half-cell potential measurements – Potential mapping on reinforced concrete structures, *Mater. Struct.* 36 (2003) 1–11.
- [9] J.A. González, A. Molina, M.L. Escudero, C. Andrade, Errors in the electrochemical evaluation of very small corrosion rates—I. polarization resistance method applied to corrosion of steel in concrete, *Corros. Sci.* 25 (1985) 917–930. doi:10.1016/0010-938X(85)90021-6.
- [10] J. Wang, Hydration mechanism of cements based on low-CO₂ clinkers containing belite, ye’elimite and calcium alumino-ferrite, in: *7th Int. Symp. Cem. Concr.*, Jinan, 2010: p. 10.
- [11] M.A.G. Aranda, A.G.D. la Torre, Sulfoaluminate cement, in: F. Pacheco-Torgal, S. Jalali, J. Labrincha, V.M. John (Eds.), *Eco-Efficient Concr.*, 1st ed., Woodhead Publishing, 2013: pp. 488–522.
- [12] M. Saifullah, L.A. Clark, Effect of Corrosion Rate on the Bond Strength of Corroded Reinforcement, in: *Corros. Corros. Prot. Steel Concr.*, 1994: pp. 591–602.
- [13] C. Alonso, C. Andrade, J. Rodriguez, J.M. Diez, Factors controlling cracking of concrete affected by reinforcement corrosion, *Mater. Struct.* 31 (1998) 435–441. doi:10.1007/BF02480466.
- [14] G.J. Al-Sulaimani, M. Kaleemullah, I.A. Basunbul, Rasheeduzzafar, Influence of corrosion and cracking on bond behavior and strength of reinforced concrete members, *ACI Struct. J.* 87 (1990) 220–231.
- [15] C. Andrade, C. Alonso, F.J. Molina, Cover cracking as a function of bar corrosion: Part I-Experimental test, *Mater. Struct.* 26 (1993) 453–464. doi:10.1007/BF02472805.
- [16] I.G. Markeset, Modelling of reinforcement corrosion in concrete-State of the art, 2008. <http://smartpipe.com/upload/Byggforsk/Publikasjoner/coin-no7.pdf>.
- [17] European Committee for Standardization, EN 206-1. Concrete - Part 1: Specification, performance, production and conformity, 2000.
- [18] U. Angst, B. Elsener, C.K. Larsen, Ø. Vennesland, Critical chloride content in reinforced concrete - A review, *Cem. Concr. Res.* 39 (2009) 1122–1138. doi:10.1016/j.cemconres.2009.08.006.
- [19] W. Morris, A. Vico, M. Vázquez, Chloride induced corrosion of reinforcing steel evaluated by concrete resistivity measurements, *Electrochim. Acta.* 49 (2004) 4447–4453. doi:10.1016/j.electacta.2004.05.001.
- [20] C. Alonso, C. Andrade, M. Castellote, P. Castro, Chloride threshold values to depassivate reinforcing bars embedded in a standardized OPC mortar, *Cem. Concr. Res.* 30 (2000) 1047–1055. doi:10.1016/S0008-8846(00)00265-9.
- [21] S. Goñi, C. Andrade, Synthetic concrete pore solution chemistry and rebar corrosion rate in the presence of chlorides, *Concr. Cem. Res.* 20 (1990) 525–539.